

Dilemma of University Selection for the Students of Baltistan Region, Pakistan

Ibrahim Hussain, Dostdar Hussain, Haji Karim Khan, Muzian Batool

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 09, 2024</p> <p>Accepted: March 10, 2025</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : University Choice Factors, University Brand, Brand Attributes</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15000863</p>	<p><i>This paper aims to highlight the factors that tend to influence the university choice of the students in Baltistan, a remote region of Gilgit-Baltistan, Pakistan. No research has been conducted so far in the region on this very important aspect of higher education. This study provides insights into the brand management issues for the universities in Gilgit-Baltistan and is of paramount importance in context of policy making for higher education institutions. A quantitative descriptive research methodology was applied to conduct the study. Findings revealed that choice of a university brand is influenced by teachers, parents, campus visit, university representative, safety, campus facilities and closeness to home. Findings have pertinent implications for higher education management. Higher educational institution should focus on those attributes that the students consider the most to attract more suitable students so that they could produce best scholars and could gain positive image in the educational market of Gilgit-Baltistan. The results of this study may also help students and their parents to understand the significant factors of university selection.</i></p>

Introduction

Students of the Baltistan region in Pakistan, generally face problems regarding the choice of universities and future career paths. Due to the limited availability of higher education opportunities in the region, students from this region generally go to the down country (other provinces of Pakistan) to continue their higher education. In doing so they face risky and expensive traveling and living costs.

Many factors affect the prospective students in developing the perceptions about universities and university life. They tend to consider various universities for their variety of fields, quality and cost and this process demands a considerable amount of time and energy. Due to the unavailability of career counseling opportunities in schools and colleges of the region, the prospective students may have a little or no knowledge about their future educational needs and university selection. This is of a paramount importance to know, how, given the circumstances, the prospective university students select universities and what factors help them in doing so. Therefore, exploring key factors or criteria which the students of Baltistan region considered during the selection process of higher educational institution were the goals of this study. It is essential to know that how the prospective students take their decisions with respect to their selection of higher educational institutions.

The emergence of educational marketing took place during 1980s within United States and United Kingdom. Research in educational branding is inadequate and an evolving area in Pakistan and this situation motivates researchers to conduct research in this field (Sabir, Ahmad, Ashraf, & Ahmad, 2013). In the contemporary scenario, competition among higher education institutions is rapidly increasing whereby public and private sector universities tend to consider students as consumers and are trying to attract most suitable students so that they could produce best scholars and could gain a positive image in the society and improve their ranking. No known research has been done so far in the context of Gilgit-Baltistan (Baltistan is one of the two regions of Gilgit-Baltistan) in terms of higher education brand management. The study aims to offer insights into the issues related to brand management of universities in Gilgit-Baltistan and has a significant role in the policy making for higher educational institutions.

The goal of this descriptive research study is also to describe certain factors that current students of Gilgit Baltistan considered while making choice of higher educational institution, and moreover, this study aims to add to the limited research in the field of university branding. Factors affecting selection of a university such as the "potential for greater engagements with teaching staff and peers, the opportunity to undertake practical industry-based experience, industry specific knowledge of the teaching staff, potential for dialogue within the class room and to build relationship with the industry and the small class sizes" were found as crucial factors that influence students' selection of universities for their higher education (Shah, Nair, & Bennett, 2013). Shah and Brown's study (as cited in Bennett, 2013) suggested that the main three factors in the university rank order are: teaching staff; courses quality; and college reputation.

Previous studies on university branding show that there is inadequate research in this area and is a new field for research (Tas&Ergin, 2012). However, in Pakistan, this has always remained a gray area.

The understanding of university persuading factors or attributes will help universities in enhancing their brand in the market. According to Keller (1993), brand elements are expressive features that make a product or service different from that of competitors. Some studies have been pertaining to the persuading factors with respect to university choice identified several persuading factors. These factors include word-of-mouth, programs quality offered by the institution, institution brand name, state of the art facilities, institution location, tuition fees level, stakeholder's relationship and network, visibility of university by communications (Iqbal, Rasli, & Hassan, 2012; Mupemhi, 2013; Shah et al., 2013).

Gray et al. (as cited in Tas&Ergin, 2012) found that the studies of university brand positioning in Asian countries by identifying some brand elements and argued that university branding is a complex task and traditional techniques for branding are not sufficient.

The research objectives of the paper are to describe the factors that persuade students to choose a university for their higher education and to know the association among the parent's socio-economic conditions and university consideration and to know whether economic opportunities affect students' choice of programs. The main questions the research is going to answer are, "what factors do prospective students consider while choosing a university?" and "is there any relationship between the socio-economic status of the parents and the universities consider by their kids?" while the third research question is "how do economic opportunities affect students' choice of program?"

This research might develop knowledge of the factors considered as influential in choice of a higher education institution. The students of Baltistan region might consider a variety of factors in their selection of universities. The research findings can be used to provide support to those who intend to develop a successful university brand inside Gilgit-Baltistan. Findings of this study will help universities in Gilgit-Baltistan to know the key motivational factors for the students when they choose a higher educational institution so as to strengthen and promote their institutions by incorporating these significant factors.

The research findings will add to knowledge on the university branding issues. Thus, the marketing managers of the universities may gain a sustainable competitive edge over their competitors. In addition, the results can provide support to parents and counselors as to understand the significant factors of university selection and can help them to choose the most appropriate university for the students.

2. Literature Review

The American Marketing Association provides definition of brand of being a name, sign, symbol, design, term or a combination of them, that provides identity to goods or services and differentiates it from competitor (Keller, 2013). David Aaker, in his book, "Building Strong Brand" proposes that a brand is a "mental box" and is concerned with imagery, feelings and thoughts that are emotionally linked to the brand in the memory of consumer (1996).

Studies have found numerous factors/attributes related to the rank order which influences students' choice of a university for their higher education. There are many reasons in investigating the factors of students' choice of universities. By knowing these influencing factors, the institution may understand the reasons behind choice of a particular institution over others and furthermore, this information helps institutions to develop the marketing strategies that are effective. This understanding of factors can also help to institutions in recognizing the expectations of students and devise effective strategies that could be implemented to improve the students' trust, satisfaction and create value for them (Shah et al., 2013).

The understanding of these persuading factors or attributes will help universities in enhancing their brand in the market. According to Keller (1993), brand attributes are the features which are descriptive and which characterize a product or service. The recruitment and attraction of brightest university students requires more effective and innovative marketing practices and for this purpose universities put focus on educational branding. Companies search for the best employees with strong educational background because the perceived value of a graduate degree is of significant importance among the employers. These factors lead to importance as well as development of efforts of the university branding efforts especially on the global scale (Tas&Ergin, 2012).

Public and private university consumers think through a wide range of measures when it comes to the choice of colleges / universities to study. However, the genuine behavior for the admission might not provide direct reflection of the significance they give to certain selection criteria (Joseph, Mullen, & Spake, 2012).

Influencing factors like the "possibility of greater engagements with peers and the teaching staff, the up to date market knowledge of the teaching staff, the chance of obtaining practical industry-based knowledge and experience and to make links with the industry and the small student professor ratio and interactive class sessions" were mentioned as main factors behind students' decision to study with private higher education institutions (Shah, Nair, & Bennett, 2013).

Ming (2010) identified some persuading factors as independent variables that persuade students to choose a specific institution for their higher education they are; the location of the institution, programs offered,

reputation of the institution, campus facilities, fee, availability of scholarship, future employment opportunities, promotional activities of the institutions, the representatives of the institution and students visit to the campus.

Gatfield, Barker, and Graham (1999) found same factors which are considered important by international students while selecting the university they are; teacher quality, resources, campus life, and direction. In a study, Mazzarol (1998) suggested factors that tend to be the potential bases for success of institutions such as, resources, coalition and image were considered among the important market success predictors. Moreover, Gray, Shyan, and Llanes (2003) identified five main brand positioning factors; learning environment of universities e.g. (excellent staff, facilities in campus, research related resources), institution reputation (university brand name, achievements and quality education), career prospect of graduates (alumni employability, expected income and employer recognition), location of the university (stability of political activities, security and generosity) and integration of cultures (freedom of practicing religion, cultural diversity) as the foremost dimensions of brand positioning when it comes to higher education institutions. Price, Matzroff, Smith and Agahi (2003) found that the facilities provided in the campus have a significant impact over choice of institution by students. These studies were focused to recognize the factors that provide help in marketing and promoting of university brand in order to attract more students. Sharma, Rao and Popli (2014) are of opinion that brands have an important part to perform in selection of business schools and business leaders require to know the variable impacts that different attributes have over brand equity, as per their perceptions and importance in mind of stakeholder.

3. Research Design

A descriptive quantitative was employed to conduct the study. Students of first year at the Karakoram International University Skardu Campus were the respondents. A structured questionnaire was adopted to collect primary data from the respondents. The quantitative approach helped us to describe the factors that help to market and promote university brand to attract more intelligent customers (students).

Every year thousands of students graduate from many educational institutions in Gilgit-Baltistan after completing their grade 12. In Pakistan, students who have completed grade twelve or under-graduate, can meet the minimum requirements to take admission in a university. Therefore, the students who have completed grade twelve and under graduate (fourteen years) of education were the population of this study. First year university students of Karakoram International University Skardu Campus were the respondents of this study.

Sample was drawn through stratified sampling technique. Population was partitioned into two strata; the students who were enrolled in post-graduate programs and the students who were enrolled in under-graduate programs, and elements were selected from each stratum randomly while the sample size of this study was 110. In the university, 73% and 27% students enrolled in the under graduate and Master's level respectively. Likewise, 63% and 37% were boys and girls respectively.

A chi-square goodness of fit shows ($X^2=2.531$, $df=1$, $p>.05$) that composition of two strata in our sample does not differ significantly from the hypothesized values that was supplied for this study, and also for the gender the result of chi-square fit ($X^2=0.209$, $df=1$, $p>.05$) showed that the sample was representative of the population.

4. Results

A total of 110 questionnaires were distributed among the students of the KIU Skardu Campus. Out of them, 96 respondents filled and returned the questionnaires. So, the response rate was 87%. The Statistical Program for the Social Sciences (SPSS 21.0) was used to prepare and analyze the data. To find normality of data Shapiro-Wilk test was used and found that the data was not normal therefore, to determine the significance of differences between groups, non-parametric tests were used.

Out of the 96 respondents 65% and 33% were boys and girls respectively. Respondents were asked to remember their last degree percentage. On an average, the respondents had scored 59% in their last academic degree. Data gathered from the respondents regarding distance from their home to the university show that, on average respondents travel twelve kilometers to reach the university campus.

The data gathered from the question about the education level of the parents of the respondents showed that both fathers' and mothers' education of the respondents was less than high school (27%) and (45%) respectively, while the responses to the question about the occupation of their parents show that most of the mothers were unemployed while most of the fathers were ordinary government employees.

Findings from the questions related to the education and occupation of students' parents answer the research question; "Is there any relationship between the socio-economic status of the parents and the college or university consideration by the students?" There was no such relationship between these variables.

Table 1:

*Pearson Chi-Square Crosstab Test
among education and occupation of
parents*

	Mothers' education	Fathers' education	Mothers' occupation	Fathers' occupation
Chi-square	25.714	25.279	23.743	39.026
df	30	30	24	36
Sig.	0.69	0.711	0.476	0.335

In Table1, a chi-square crosstab analysis shows that no statistical relationship exists between educational and occupational background of parents and choosing a university by their children ($X^2 = 25.714$, $df=30$, $p>.05$), ($X^2 = 25.279$, $df=30$, $p>.05$), and ($X^2 = 39.062$, $df=36$, $p>.05$), ($X^2 = 23.743$, $df=24$, $p>.05$).

4.1 Values and goals

In response to the questions about the values and goals of the students, findings showed that 84.0% students responded that in their families it was already considered that they would pursue a university degree after completing their high school. Most of the respondents (38.9%) started thinking to attend university education at their higher secondary level.

The findings for the question "whether they wanted to pursue higher education", 74% responded with 'yes', and only 6% opted for 'no' and the remaining were not sure whether or not they would pursue their studies. University education is a valued goal for most of the respondents who want to pursue their higher education (74%) and for the rest of the respondents obtaining a current degree was the primary goal.

"How do economic opportunities affect students' program choice?". The findings for this question showed that most of the students (58%) believed economic conditions and future employment opportunities affected their choice of a program.

A chi-square crosstab analysis showed that there was a significant difference among the students having different programs and the future employment opportunity ($X^2 = 14.190$, $df=5$, $p<.05$).

For respondents who believe economic opportunities affect their choice of program, 77% respondents were from the department of educational development, 71% were from Master of Business Administration, 67% were from Bachelor of Business Administration and 33% were from BS-Computer Sciences. These departments should have more market linkages so as to transfer market-oriented knowledge to these students to get their maximum satisfaction.

Sources of information

In order to determine comparative ratings for sources of information such as the persons, contacts and significant factors, categories five and four (high important) were combined and categories one and two (low important) were combined while category three is set as neutral.

As shown in Figure 1 and 2, students rated the most important persons and contacts are; Teachers (92%), Fathers (91%), Mother (80%) visit to campus (67%), university representative (67%), former student recommendation (58%).

Figure-3 shows the most important factors of significance are; Safety (92%), campus facilities (90%), campus environment and closeness to home (89%), scholarships (86%), specialized program offered (85%), reputation of institution (82%), availability of housing and tuition cost (81%). A chi-square analysis indicates that there was a significant difference exists between boys and girls respondents for Mother (boys 71% and girls 97%), religious advisor (boys 39% and girls 69%) and university reputation (boys 77% and girls 100%) and an insignificant difference exist for teacher (boys 89% and girls 97%), father (boys 86% and girls 100%), university website (boys 57% and girls 73%), former student recommendation (boys 62% and girls 53%), campus visit (boys 63% and girls 73%), university representation (boys 63% and girls 73%), closeness to home (boys 87% and girls 94%), campus facilities (boys 86% and girls 100%), safety (boys 90% and girls 100%), campus environment (boys 86% and girls 97%), scholarships (boys 86% and girls 91%), specialized programs offered (boys 82% and girls 94%), availability of housing (boys 88% and girls 78%), tuition fee (boys 84% and girls 79%). In selection of a university for higher studies most of the girls students consult with their mothers, religious advisors and

consider university reputation, it is therefore to attract more suitable female students these elements must be given a special attention by the university authorities while remaining factors have equally important for both male and female students.

Figure 4 shows that majority of the students indicated that they considered and applied to only two to three universities like Quaid-e-Azam university (QAU), National University of Modern Languages (NUML) and Karachi University (KU). Thus, these universities have emerged as the most potential competitors for the universities of Baltistan region.

Figure-5 shows that most of the students indicated that they were unable to attend their first-choice university due to the factors like, “too far distance from home (73%)”, “cost factor (21%)”, and “GPA low (5%)”.

It is risky and costly for students of Baltistan region to go to developed cities of the country while the findings show that students do not want to get admission too far from their homes to be safe, and to minimize cost of their higher education. It also shows that for most of the students Karakoram International University (Skardu Campus) was not their first-choice university but due to distance and cost factors most of the students were compelled to get admission in their home town.

Students were asked “how do they feel now about their choice?” most of the students (47%) were fully satisfied with their choice and only 12% said that they were not satisfied with their decision while 41% said that they were feeling good about their choice of the university.

Discussion

A quantitative approach was used to explore the key factors considered by the first-year students of the Karakoram International University, Skardu Campus in connection with their university choices. Findings have shown that teachers and parents are the most influential people for students during their selection of a higher educational institution. It was found that university reputation, visit to a campus and the university website were the key persuasive factors and information sources. The recommendation of former students was another source of influencing factor for the students. Likewise, the respondents rated campus safety, campus facilities, campus

environment, and closeness to home, availability of scholarships and specialized programs offered as crucial factors in their choice. Marketing strategies must be devised to promote the features of the institution which are given importance by students. Other researchers such as Iqbal et al (2012), Mupemhi, (2013) and Shah et al (2013a) also reported similar findings in their respective studies.

However, teachers from the category of influential persons, as well as safety, and campus environment from other influential significant factors, are unique factors of this study. Patton (2000) also found that the most important factor behind the university selection was word-of-mouth along with other associated factors including campus facilities, courses offered, distance, and fee ratios as important factors. Likewise, Shahid, Shafique, and Bodla (2012) also identified the word-of-mouth as most significant factor with respect to a university choice, along with other factors including university environment and social conditions that are also the basis of positive word of mouth. Studies conducted on the international students' choices of a university selection show that international students are different from domestic students on seven choice factors including on-campus housing, recommendation from family, academic reputation, reputation of faculty, participation in intercollegiate sports, printed material or video and need-based financial aid (Alfattal, 2017).

5. Conclusion and Recommendations:

Findings of the study suggest some pertinent implications for the universities across the country especially for those who provide higher education services in similar settings. Since, results of this study indicate that teachers and parents are the most influential people for the students in their selection of the higher education institutions. Therefore, it is recommended that universities should focus on teachers and parents among other important attributes, in their promotional campaigns to gain and maintain a competitive advantage over competitors. It is recommended that the university management should treat branding of their universities as a strategic concern and that an organization-wide approach to quality service delivery is needed if the university is to be perceived favorably by the students. Further research can be done on a broader scale, by using both qualitative and quantitative approaches at a further level. For instance, the study can be further extended by measuring consumer-based brand equity of different universities which can be used to improve positioning and university brand image.

References

- Aaker, D. A. (2012). *Building strong brands*: Simon and Schuster.
- Gatfield, T., Barker, M., & Graham, P. (1999). Measuring communication impact for university advertising materials. *Corporate Communications: An International Journal*, 4(2), 73-79.
- Iqbal, M. J., Rasli, A. B. M., & Hassan, I. (2012). University Branding: A Myth or a Reality. *Pak. J. Commer. Soc. Sci.*
- Joseph, M., Mullen, E. W., & Spake, D. (2012). University branding: Understanding students' choice of an educational institution. *Journal of Brand Management*, 20(1), 1-12. doi: 10.1057/bm.2012.13
- Keller, K. L. (2013). *Strategic Brand Management* (4 ed.). England: Pearson.
- Mazzarol, T. (1998). Critical success factors for international education marketing. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 12(4), 163-175. doi: doi:10.1108/09513549810220623
- Mupemhi, S. (2013). Factors influencing choice of a university by students in Zimbabwe. *African Journal of Business Management*, 7(36), 3723-3729. doi: 10.5897/AJBM2013.7077
- Price, I., Matzdorf, F., Smith, L., & Agahi, H. (2003). The impact of facilities on student choice of university. *Facilities*, 21(10), 212-222.
- Sabir, R. I., Ahmad, W., Ashraf, R. U., & Ahmad, N. (2013). Factors Affecting University and Course Choice: A Comparison of Undergraduate Engineering and Business Students in Central Punjab, Pakistan. *Journal of Basic and Applied Scientific*, 3(10), 298-305.
- Shah, M., Nair, C. S., & Bennett, L. (2013a). Factors influencing student choice to study at private higher education institutions. www.emeraldinsight.com/0968-4883.htm.
- Shah, M., Nair, C. S., & Bennett, L. (2013b). Factors influencing student choice to study at private higher education institutions. *Quality Assurance in Education*, 21(4), 402-416. doi: 10.1108/QAE-042012-0019
- Tas, A., & Ergin, E. A. (2012). Key Factors for Student Recruitment: The Issue of University Branding. *International Business Research*, 5(10).
- Alfattal, E. (2017). International students' college choice is different! *International Journal of Educational Management*, 31(7), 930-943. doi: doi:10.1108/IJEM-05-2016-0095
- Shahid, H., Shafique, O., & Bodla, O. (2012). What factors affect a student's choice of a university for higher education. *Research on Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(10), 64-67.
- Sharma, A. A., Rao, V. R., & Popli, S. (2014). Measuring consumer-based brand equity for Indian business schools. *Journal of Marketing for Higher Education*, 23(2), 175-203. doi: 10.1080/08841241.2013.866609

Author Information

Ibrahim Hussain,

Lecturer, University of Baltistan, Skardu, Gilgit-Baltistan, Pakistan

Dostdar Hussain

Lecturer, University of Baltistan, Skardu, Gilgit-Baltistan, Pakistan

Haji Karim Khan, PhD

Assistant Professor, Department of Educational Development, University of Baltistan, Skardu

Muzian Batool

Lecturer, University of Baltistan, Skardu, Gilgit-Baltistan, Pakistan
